

Synthesis and characterization of 1,2,4-triazole containing Schiff base ligands and their Cu^{II} complexes

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Abstract : The condensation of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole with 4-(diethylamino)salicylaldehyde, 5-Br-salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde in methanol to produce 1,2,4-triazole containing Schiff base ligands 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-(diethylamino)phenol (**L¹H**), 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-4-bromophenol (**L²H**) and 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-methoxyphenol (**L³H**) respectively. The ligands on reaction with Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in 2 : 1 molar ratio form Cu^{II} complexes (1-3) of general formula CuL₂. The ligands and the complexes were characterized by means elemental analysis, FTIR, NMR, Mass, UV-Visible spectroscopy, luminescence spectroscopy. Electrochemical study on the ligands exhibit one oxidation peak due to phenol to phenoxyl radical and one or two reduction wave/s, while the Cu complexes show Cu^{II/III} oxidation and one ligand based reduction. Cu^{I/II} oxidation is masked inside the ligand based reduction processes.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazole, Schiff base, UV-Vis spectra, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

The synthesis of Schiff base is of substantial interest due to their wide application in many chemical and biological aspects. Transition metal complexes of N,O-donor ligands such as Schiff bases have attracted a lot of interest due to their effective biological activities and also have found pharmaceutical and therapeutic applications¹⁻⁴. The Schiff bases of azomethine nitrogen donor heterocyclic ligands with 1,2,4-triazole systems are well known due to their wide range of pharmaceutical applications as anti-inflammatory⁵, analgesic⁶, antibacterial^{7,8}, antifungal⁹⁻¹¹, antiviral¹², antitumoral¹³, anticonvulsant¹⁴, antidepressant¹⁵ and anticancer agents¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Metal complexes containing 1,2,4-triazole moiety find applications as magnetic materials¹⁹⁻²¹, photophysically active materials²² and therapeutic agents²³.

From the synthetic point Schiff base has always been an automatic choice due to its ease of preparation. Very often serendipitous results are obtained from the Schiff base complexes which have attracted the coordination chemist.

In our ongoing interest on the chemistry of new complexes with N,O-donor Schiff base ligands, we synthe-

sized and characterized 1,2,4-triazole containing Schiff base ligands and their Cu complexes. The general structure of prepared ligands and their Cu^{II} complexes are shown in Fig. 1. Both ligands and the complexes have been characterized by Mass, NMR, IR, UV-Visible spectra, luminescence and electrochemical study.

Ligand : R = 4-Et₂N (**L¹H**),
5-Br (**L²H**),
4-OMe (**L³H**)
Complex : [Cu(**L¹**)₂] (**1**),
[Cu(**L²**)₂] (**2**),
[Cu(**L³**)₂] (**3**)

Fig. 1. General structure of the ligands and complexes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The condensation of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole with 4-(diethylamino)salicylaldehyde, 5-Br-salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-5-methoxybenzaldehyde in a molar ratio 1 : 1 in the presence of methanol (Scheme 1) were used for the synthesis of **L¹H**, **L²H** and **L³H** respectively. The Cu^{II}

where R = 4-Et₂N (**L**¹**H**), 5-Br (**L**²**H**), 4-OMe (**L**³**H**)

Scheme 1. The general reaction scheme for the synthesis of Schiff bases.

complexes (**1-3**) were prepared by the reaction of Schiff base ligands in 2 : 1 molar ratio with Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in methanolic solution. Equivalent amount of Et₃N was used to deprotonate the phenolic-OH functionality for the complexation.

Electronic spectra :

The UV-Visible spectrum of all the ligands and its complexes were recorded in DMF solution. In the UV region all the ligands show one or more intraligand charge transfer. Such types of transitions are observed for **L**¹**H** at 365 nm, for **L**²**H** at 273, 338 and 402 nm and for **L**³**H** at 277 nm and 357 nm. In the UV region all the complexes preserve these intra ligand transitions in the observed spectrum. The observed peaks may be assigned on the basis of the existing literature for the Cu complex^{24–26}. The peak at 365 nm in complex **1** is of intra ligand nature, while phenolate-Cu LMCT (Ligand metal charge transfer) transition for complex **1** is observed at 488 nm which appear in the form of shoulder. Complex **2** also shows intraligand transitions at 272 and 338 nm. In addition **2** also display a peak at 454 nm (Fig. S11) which may be assigned to phenolate-Cu LMCT transition. Complex **3** shows two transitions of intraligand character at 278, 364 nm whereas the peak at 420 nm is of phenolate-Cu LMCT nature (Fig. S12). All the complexes are capable of exhibiting the d-d band in the lower energy region : (700–756) nm in Fig. 2. Such d-d electronic transitions appear at 700 nm, 734 nm and 756 nm for complex **1**, **2** and **3** respectively.

Luminescence spectra :

1,2,4-Triazole moiety is 6-electrons π -excessive system, so it may enhance the emissive property when appended to a molecular system. In the present study we have also observed moderate to high emissive nature in the molecules.

Fig. 2. Absorbance spectra of all the complexes in visible region in DMF.

A typical concentration of (1×10^{-5}) M solution was used for **L**¹**H**, **L**²**H**, complex **1**, and complex **2**, while for **L**³**H** and complex **3** (5×10^{-7}) M solution was used for the luminescence measurements. On exciting at 365 nm, **L**¹**H** and complex **1** show luminescence at 431 nm, excitation of **L**²**H** and complex **2** at 338 nm causes emission at 432 and 510 nm, while **L**³**H** and complex **3** emits at 448 nm while excited at 278 nm (Fig. 3). The ligands and corresponding Cu complexes have similar emission spectra. This confirms that the photophysical processes in the complexes are ligand centered. For **L**¹**H**, **L**²**H** and corresponding Cu complexes the emission intensity are almost same, but complex **3** shows almost double emission intensity than that of ligand **L**³**H**. Relative emission intensity of the ligands decrease in the order **L**¹**H** > **L**³**H** > **L**²**H**. This may be due to the higher electron donating nature of Et₂N- and -OMe in comparison to electron withdrawing Br-attached to the respective phenol group. However the coordination induced enhancement of the emission in complex **3** with respect to the

Fig. 3. Luminescence spectra of all the ligands and its Cu^{II} complexes in DMF.

corresponding ligand L^3H may be due the rigidity of the bonds in the excited state along with the suitable size of the -OMe group which induces further stabilization of the excited state.

Electrochemical investigation :

The electrochemical behavior of the ligands and their Cu^{II} complexes have been investigated by cyclic voltammetry in DMF medium. The ligands L^2H and L^3H show one prominent irreversible oxidation wave at 0.56 V and 1.12 V respectively during the anodic scan. L^1H doesn't display this oxidation. This oxidation process may be due to oxidation of phenolic-OH to phenoxyl radical. This electrochemical process is also obtained for the complexes where the oxidation is due to phenoxide ion to phenoxyl radical. Complex 1, 2 and 3 show an irreversible peak at 1.05 V, 0.59 V and 1.22 V respectively. In the anodic scan the complexes show another oxidation process in lower potential which can be described as $\text{Cu}^{\text{II/III}}$ oxidation. The observed potentials are 0.82 V, 0.35 V and 0.72 V for complex 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

The observed electrochemical oxidation process as manifested by cyclic voltammogram can be rationalized as follows. Ligand L^1H and L^3H contains $-\text{NEt}_2$ and -OMe group at the *meta* position of the phenolic-OH group in the salicylaldehyde ring. Both these groups have +R and -I effect. At *meta* position +R effect does not work on the phenolic-OH, but -I effect may operate to some extent. This reduces the electron density on phenolic-

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of L^1H and 1 in (a), L^2H and 2 in (b), L^3H and 3 in (c) in DMF solution with TBAP as supporting electrolyte in glassy carbon electrode at 100 mV/s^{-1} .

OH. This causes both the oxidation processes; i.e. phenol to phenoxyl radical in the ligand and phenoxide to phenoxyl radical in the complexes **1** and **3** as well as Cu^{II/III} non favorable. Therefore the observed oxidation potential values are relatively high. In **L²H**, the Br-group (also having -I and +R effect) at the *para* position to the phenolic-OH group does not have any residual effect on the electron density on the phenolic-OH as +R effect is small and -I effect is insignificant due to distance. Since there is no removal of electron density from phenolic-O, the oxidation potentials are lowered for both the process in **L²H** and complex **2**. On the reduction side both the ligands and the corresponding complexes show one or more ligand based reduction processes. We can't observe or separate the Cu^{II/I} process which most probably is obscured under the strong ligand based reduction waves.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

All reagents and chemicals were purchased from commercial sources like E. Merck, Fluka and Aldrich and used without further purification. All solvents used for synthesis were A.R. grade and used as receive. HPLC grade DMF was used for spectroscopic and electrochemical studies.

Elemental analyses were performed on an Elementar Vario EL III C, H, N, S and O analyzer. Infrared spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Shimadzu IR-Prestige21 spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 750 spectrophotometer. Fluorescence spectra of all the ligand and complexes were recorded in the DMF solution, at room temperature, using a Shimadzu RF-5301 PC spectrofluorophotometer. Electrochemical measurements of all the ligands and complexes were recorded in a CHI6003E potentiostat in DMF medium using glassy carbon working electrode, Pt wire counter electrode, Ag/AgCl non aqueous reference electrode and 0.1 M TBAP (tetrabutylammonium perchlorate) as supporting electrolyte. The ferrocene/ferrocenium couple was observed at E^0 (ΔE_p) = 0.1 V (100 mV) under these experimental conditions. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE DPX 500 MHz spectrometer using Si(CH₃)₄ as internal standard. ESI-MS spectra of the samples were recorded on JEOL JMS 600 instrument.

Synthesis of the ligands :

Synthesis of 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-(diethylamino)phenol (**L¹H**) :

2-((4*H*-1,2,4-Triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-(diethylamino)phenol was synthesized by refluxing a solution of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.42 g, 5 mmol) and 4-(diethylamino)salicylaldehyde (0.96 g, 5 mmol) in methanol for 12 h. When the solution was cooled at room temperature a white crystalline solid of Schiff base **L¹H** was obtained. Yield : 72%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₇N₅O : C, 60.21; H, 6.61; N, 27.01. Found : C, 60.12; H, 6.43; N, 26.92%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3109, 2966, 1616, 1516, 1361; NMR (¹H, 500 MHz, CDCl₃) : 10.21 (1H, O-H), 8.47 (2H, ArH), 8.41 (1H, ArH), 7.26 (1H, ArH), 6.1–6.2 (2H, ArH), 3.37–3.41 (4H, CH₂), 1.18–1.21 (6H, CH₃); MS : m/z 282 [M+Na].

Synthesis of 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-4-bromophenol (**L²H**) :

2-((4*H*-1,2,4-Triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-4-bromophenol was synthesized by the reaction of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.42 g, 5 mmol) and 5-Br-salicylaldehyde (1.00 g, 5 mmol) in methanol. A white crystalline solid of Schiff base (**L²H**) was prepared by similar procedure as for, ligand (**L¹H**). Yield : 68%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for C₉H₇BrN₄O : C, 40.47; H, 2.64; N, 20.98. Found : C, 40.12; H, 2.43; N, 20.92%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3213, 3093, 3035, 1612, 1500, 628; NMR (¹H, 500 MHz, DMSO) : 10.80 (1H, O-H), 9.18 (2H, ArH), 9.09 (1H, ArH), 7.89 (1H, ArH), 7.54–7.56 (1H, ArH), 6.95–6.97 (1H, ArH); MS : m/z 266 [M+].

Synthesis of 2-((4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-methoxyphenol (**L³H**) :

2-((4*H*-1,2,4-Triazole-4-ylimino)methyl)-5-methoxyphenol was synthesized by the reaction of 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.42 g, 5 mmol) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.76 g, 5 mmol) in methanol. A yellow crystalline solid of Schiff base (**L³H**) was prepared by similar procedure as for, ligand (**L¹H**). Yield : 73%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₀N₄O₂ : C, 55.05; H, 4.62; N, 25.68. Found : C, 55.11; H, 4.43; N, 25.72%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν 3124, 2962, 2654, 1604, 1504; NMR (¹H, 500 MHz, DMSO) : 10.05 (1H, O-H), 9.16 (1H, ArH), 9.11 (1H, ArH), 7.27–7.28 (1H, ArH), 7.03–7.05 (1H, ArH), 6.92–6.94 (1H, ArH), 3.73 (3H, CH₃); MS :

m/z 240 [M+Na].

Synthesis of the complexes :

The 2 equivalent of prepared ligands was completely dissolved in methanol. 2 equivalent of Et_3N were added to the ligand solution. 1 equivalent of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methanol was mixed and refluxed for 5 h and the product was isolated and purified according to the particular procedure described below.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2]$ (**1**) : $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.29 g, 0.8 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) and L^1H (0.41 g, 1.6 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) were reacted as described above. A light green precipitate of complex **1** was washed by methanol and ether, finally dried in vacuum. Yield : 57%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{Cu}-\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_2$: C, 53.83; H, 5.56; N, 24.14. Found : C, 53.82; H, 5.53; N, 24.42%; UV-Vis (DMF) : $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) : 365 (33218), 488sh (804), 700 (367); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : ν 3116, 2978, 1631, 1589, 1523, 1095; MS : m/z 580 [M+].

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2]$ (**2**) : $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.29 g, 0.8 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) and L^2H (0.42 g, 1.6 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) were reacted as described above. A green precipitate of complex **2** was washed by methanol and ether, finally dried in vacuum. Yield : 52%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{Cu}-\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_8\text{O}_2$: C, 36.29; H, 2.03; N, 18.81. Found : C, 36.21; H, 2.05; N, 18.14%; UV-Vis (DMF) : $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) : 272 (12694), 338 (6810), 454 (1460), 734 (293); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : ν 3510, 3290, 3120, 1612, 1539, 1099, 624; MS : m/z 596 [M+1].

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^3)_2]$ (**3**) : $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.29 g, 0.8 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) and L^3H (0.34 g, 1.6 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) were reacted as described above. A green precipitate of complex **3** was washed by methanol and ether, finally dried in vacuum. Yield : 61%. Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{Cu}-\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_8\text{O}_4$: C, 48.24; H, 3.64; N, 22.50. Found : C, 48.28; H, 3.44; N, 22.81%; UV-Vis (DMF) : $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) : 278 (29335), 364 (6838), 420 (8509), 756 (338); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : ν 3124, 2962, 2654, 1604, 1504, 1215, 1041; MS : m/z 499 [M+1].

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